

D7.2 – Interim dissemination and communication plan and report 1

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the interim Dissemination and Communication Plan and Report 1 for the ARIADNEplus project. The report covers the first 18 months of the dissemination and communication activities undertaken by the lead team at PIN Scrl and all the (40+) partners who are involved in the project. Since the report *D2.2 Initial Report on Networking and Integration* covers the dissemination activities in detail, this report focusses more on the communication activities whilst providing an overview of all the activities undertaken by the project in Section 3. Section 4 concerns the plan for the next period, M19-M36 and highlights the new initiatives to be undertaken during this period.

The first Dissemination and Communication Plan identified the different stakeholders and described how these may be reached. During the first period, the project partners and their organisations were the main focus for dissemination and communication. The Community Needs Survey generated a lot of interest within the archaeological community with over 700 responses. The Joint Directors, Franco Niccolucci (PIN) and Julian Richards (ADS) have also been active in establishing connections in Europe, the USA and Argentina. Information and news have been published on the website, which is aimed at a wider audience, and other methods of communication include partner mailing lists, social media channels and the Project Newsletter.

The ARIADNEplus website has met its M18 targets with Twitter and Facebook being major sources of referral. A modified design has just been launched with new content being added in the form of a Training Hub (providing training resources) and with a set of short videos for communicating the scientific results of the project planned for Period 2. In addition, the translated pages have been made more prominent in order to improve better communication for non-native English speakers. A comprehensive set of promotional materials were produced for the kick-off meeting at PIN in February 2019 and these along with leaflets, were used by the partners to promote the project at conferences and events where they attend and present. The Newsletter has a good opening rate (recipients have opened the email to read the Newsletter) at over 40% and the subscriber list has grown slowly but steadily.

The Partners have attended several conferences and workshops, giving presentations and taking part in round tables and workshops. More recently, as events have gone virtual, ARIADNEplus has featured in a Twitter Conference (“DH in the Time of Virus”) in April and then in May, co-organised the “European web conference on 3D digital cultural heritage for resilience, recovery and sustainability” which was streamed via YouTube. ARIADNEplus has also produced a number of papers along with the book “The ARIADNE Impact” which is a collection of 17 papers contributed by the partners and is published by Archeolingua. This has already been viewed over 700 times on Zenodo with 550 downloads. In terms of training, the first Transnational access (TNA) call was very successful, attracting 16 applications of which 13 were successful. Unfortunately, most of the visits have had to be postponed and the summer schools cancelled for this year but the next call is planned for September for in-house training during 2021.

The Communication and dissemination plan for M19-M36 describes the new website design and objectives. The new content includes the Training Hub, short videos and there will also be some new printed materials (e.g. a poster), publications and internal reports. CAA and EAA are the two major conferences to be targeted by the project, with some attention paid to events relating to the new fields of research such as Bio-Archaeology, aDNA and Environmental Studies as well as those attended by computer scientists.

2 Introduction and objectives

Work package 7 is responsible for the definition of an overall communication and dissemination planning and strategy, along with the co-ordination of training. The main activities undertaken are largely communication of project activities and results to a wide range of identified stakeholders. These communication activities¹ also require the support of the project partners, e.g. using their own media channels to promote the project action. Work package 2 focusses on the more specific activities of networking and integration and which involves the partners disseminating the results of the project through meetings, workshops, papers and training, for example, to their peers within the research community. Work package 7 in turn supports Work package 2 by advertising the networking and integration activities, making resources available (such as reports) and promoting the Transnational Access and other training activities.

As the deliverable D2.2 Initial Report on Networking and Integration covers much of the dissemination activity for M1-M18, this deliverable mainly focuses upon the communication activity for M1-M18 and the planning for M19-M36 for future communication and dissemination activities.

The COVID-19 pandemic had a profound impact on our work and communication since late February and has made face-to-face meetings and events impossible. Nearly all our activities are currently digital and mainly conducted in cyberspace. Even as we start to return to our more normal lives, we still have to practice social distancing, foreign travel is still problematic and it seems it will take several months, if not years, before large social gatherings such as conferences will happen again. The ARIADNEplus community has adapted very well to this seismic change, carrying on their work from home and using Skype and Zoom to meet virtually and have discussions and meetings with partners and colleagues. Fortunately, the dissemination and communication strategy is largely digital, but the current situation has still forced a reassessment of how we can be more effective, and what we can do to replace the lost dissemination opportunities of major European conferences, such as CAA and EAA. Some innovative solutions are presented in this report along with our adapted plans for the next 18 months, as we all deal with the new reality.

3 Report on Dissemination and Communication M1-M18

3.1 Reaching the stakeholder community

ARIADNEplus has a wide range of stakeholders² who have varying priorities and interests. By developing an understanding of the needs and interests of each group, the project aims to make its dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organisations interested in using the research infrastructure. Awareness of the needs of community helps identify the best channels for contacting stakeholder groups (such as email lists, conferences, other means) and in the design and planning of dissemination materials and activities, thus helping to raise the visibility of the project and promote use of its outputs:

- internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities;

¹ Making the Most of Your H2020 Project

Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation - the European IPR Helpdesk

² Please refer to D7.1 for detailed descriptions of each one of these identified stakeholders.

- research institutions active in the field as represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties such as deans, directors etc.;
- scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines and the wider scientific community;
- international networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- cultural Heritage institutions interested in activities such as data management and training;
- commercial organisations such as private companies involved in archaeology, cultural heritage and consultancy;
- semi-professional and amateur organisations and groups;
- media and the public at large.

For the purposes of this report, we will summarise how each of these stakeholders has been addressed by the current strategy, along with activities and plans for M19-M36.

To date, the main focus of the project dissemination has been on the internal stakeholders, keeping them up to date with the various activities going on in the different sub-groups, co-ordinating contributions to workshops and conferences and in turn, relying on them to forward and disseminate information within their own organisations and through their own media/social media channels. Basecamp has, therefore, been used as the main means of communication internally and all partners are signed up to the newsletters, mainly as a reminder to visit the website. Twitter is also widely used among the researchers. Likewise, research institutions are reached through these networks, as subscribers to newsletters and blogs and as followers on Twitter. Attendance at physical events during the first 12 months or so was also an effective method for communicating the project activities. The project has already gained an additional associate project member, the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences based in Heidelberg, Germany who will be providing metadata for their paleo-anthropology database (the ROAD database) from the ROCEEH project (The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans). Many of these dissemination activities are the networking and integration activities described in D2.2 Initial Report on Networking and Integration.

The ARIADNEplus Community Needs Survey was run from May 25th to September 4th, 2019 and received over 700 responses (of which 484 were sufficiently complete to be included in the analysis). This is a high level of engagement and the figures for the background of the (valid) respondents indicate that the project is succeeding in reaching across the stakeholder community:

Organisational background: 53% university or public research organisation, 19% museum, 15% governmental institution, 8% private company or research institute; 2% not affiliated with an organisation (e.g. self-employed, free-lancing), 3% other.

As might be expected, the majority of participants came from publicly-funded organisations or similar (some museums were privately owned) but the remaining participants (13%) were from private companies or self-employed/freelance with 3% classified as “Other”. The survey was not aimed at the general public but the “Other” could include people from semi-professional and amateur organisations and groups.

Regarding international collaboration, Joint Project Director Franco Niccolucci took part in the joint SAA/EAA workshop on Human Migration, organized by CfAS (the Coalition for Archaeological Synthesis) of which ARIADNEplus is now a member. He later travelled to Argentina to introduce ARIADNEplus at a conference hosted by partner Andrés Izeta. The other Joint Project Director Julian Richards was in Boston in January 2020 and at Arizona State University’s Center for Digital Antiquity

in February, where it was agreed to establish a consortium on FAIR Archaeology – ARIADNEplus is one of the founding members. A proposal for a series of workshops for the NSF is being developed.

ARIADNEplus is also co-ordinating training and dissemination activities with the SEADDA COST Action, the two having several members in common. For example, the two organisations disseminate information about each other’s training workshops and cooperate on certain activities where there is a mutual joint benefit. One of these was for a joint session at EAA Budapest, 26-30 August, 2020 Session 350: “Sustainability, unsustainability and opportunity for archaeological data” which will still take place, but as a virtual session.

In terms of communication, the website aims to reach all the stakeholders which also includes the public and third parties. Whilst English is used widely in the research community, this not always the case outside so several of the website pages have been translated into the other main European Languages (Italian, Greek, English, Slovenian, Czech, Bulgarian, Polish, Hungarian, French, German, Spanish, Swedish and Dutch) to facilitate a wider understanding of the project aims, especially in central and eastern Europe where many of the countries have not been previously involved in ARIADNE.

3.1.1 Resources amongst the consortium and externally

The ARIADNE consortium consists of partners in 27 countries including Belgium, Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Finland, Iceland, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Cyprus, Israel, Croatia, Romania and Bulgaria. From outside of Europe, there are partners from Argentina, the US and Japan. CARARE, as a membership organisation, also includes other countries within its membership such as Lithuania. During the first period, the partners have been very active in disseminating news about the project. Activities have included:

- Creating links to the ARIADNEplus website from the partners’ own site (all partners)
- Giving presentations at national and international events
- Organising ARIADNE workshops at international conferences
- Distributing ARIADNE dissemination materials
- Distributing notices about ARIADNE activities to mailing lists
- Writing articles about ARIADNE activities for in-house newsletters
- Contributing articles to the ARIADNE website
- Contributing articles to local newspapers and television
- Disseminating news and information about ARIADNE via the social networks
- Participating in meetings organized by research infrastructures, projects and international initiatives and giving presentations about ARIADNE and/or distributing materials

For example, Nara has disseminated information about the research infrastructure in their local region. Articles about the project have been published in the most respected Japanese newspaper, Asahi Shimbun, and on two regional newspapers (Nara Shimbun and Yomiuri Shimbun) about how NARA is the first organisation from Asia to participate in ARIADNEplus which will help archaeological information to become accessible worldwide, and improve the management of digital data. In addition, a feature was broadcast on the NHK television channel. (See news item: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/nara-spreads-the-word-about-ariadneplus-in-japan/>).

3.1.2 Information and news

The project has communicated information and news about the project's activities and related areas via the project website, a project newsletter, social media channels and (to a more limited extent) to the press. A dedicated section of the project website has been established for news:

Figure 1. Screen shot of ARIADNEplus News section.

In addition, a new 'Features' section was added where longer articles on more general topics related to the project and archaeology can be found, these being aimed more at the general public and interested third parties. To date, two articles have been published, one on archaeology in the US and one on the Survey Results which summarises the key findings.

3.1.3 Internal communication channels

Two main forms of internal communication are being used within the project at present: Basecamp and D4Science. Basecamp is the main platform used for "broadcasting" information and requests to all involved (there are 174 people registered from all the partners), often with links to supporting documentation in the project depository which is held in D4Science. Within Basecamp, there are around 30 sub-groups (for targeted messaging). Since WP4 has been the main focus of activity during the first 18 months, the sub-groups assigned to each sub-task for Task 4.4 have been very active. Since updates have been provided in Basecamp and all the partners who are working on content for the Portal are basically following the same process with domain variations, there has been no need for

‘internal newsletters’ at this stage of the project and it appears that posts in Basecamp are meeting the internal communication needs, especially as participants are able to interact and discuss topics of interest. For example, there have been discussions on why the Getty AAT is being used and not Wikidata (in fact, both can be used together) and currently the partners are debating which Open Source software licence is preferred.

For those partners who are directly involved in the technical development of the Portal, D4Science is the preferred means of communication. Currently, there are two main VREs, each with their own messaging channel:

1. ARIADNEplus_Mappings – this is the environment in which everything concerning mapping strategies and tools happens. From here it is also possible to access the 3M and Vocabulary mapping tools.
2. ARIADNEplus_AggregationManagement – this is reserved for the small team in charge of coordinating the aggregation of the partners’ metadata.

3.1.4 Mailing lists

Several partners have mailing lists, along with their own social media channels. When the project has an announcement that requires dissemination, the information is posted in Basecamp and the relevant partners will then forward this as appropriate. A recent example of such a posting was for the European web conference on 3D digital cultural heritage for resilience, recovery and sustainability on the 27th May 2020 and last year for the first Transnational Access call in September which elicited a good response from the partners.

3.1.5 Social networks

The main social network used by the project is Twitter, with a small Facebook presence for key postings such as the first TNA call. Many of the partners also have Twitter feeds which are used to retweet ARIADNEplus tweets. The project also has membership of a number of archaeology-related LinkedIn groups and these were used to advertise the first TNA call. In addition, ARIADNEplus has continued uploading reports and presentations of wider interest to the Slideshare account established for the original project.

3.2 The ARIADNEplus website

The ARIADNEplus website and Twitter are the two main communication channels for the wider stakeholder community.

3.2.1 The ARIADNEplus website

The ARIADNEplus website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) was launched in month two of the project was introduced to the project partners at the kick-off meeting held in Prato on 11-14 February 2019. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to all stakeholders and to related projects, and also provide a single point of access to the research infrastructure via the Portal. The graphic solution used for the website frontend is based on a responsive design, that can adapt to the user’s behaviour and environment based on screen size, platform and orientation.

Since the launch, some minor updates have been made to the website with the addition of new content such as the Features section and the translations of the main information pages (c.f. 4.1.2).

Figure 2. The Home page.

The News and Events pages have been updated regularly. Since February, 12 events have been posted along with 20 news items. At the start of the second year, a separate section was created for training resources. The specific topics have been guided by the response to the Community Needs Survey, where a high level of interest was indicated in all of the proposed subject matter. Although the project will be creating some resources (e.g. from workshops and for the Portal), content has also been sourced from third parties to provide coverage, and this will be launched during M18. Further information on the Training Hub is given in the planning for M19-M36 (c.f. Section 4.3) as more content will be added during this period.

3.2.1.1 Transnational Access web pages

The first Transnational Access call was made at the beginning of September 2019 after the summer vacation period. All the information about the call, including the application process, was published on the website and disseminated widely across social media, newsletters and partner networks. The 2019 Call has now been moved to a new sub-page (TNA 2019 Call (Closed)) since this allows researchers browsing the website and TNA section to read the requirements which will be the same for the 2020 call and for any future candidates to make a note in their diary to watch out for the next call.

3.2.1.2 Summary pages for the public in native languages

In order to foster more engagement with the public and non-professionals interested in archaeology and to raise awareness about the ARIADNE Infrastructure further afield within the archaeology community, many of the partners translated a set of three pages into their own language during the first few months of the project, with the new sub-site being launched in October (M10). The three pages are aimed at Researchers, Heritage Managers and Professional and Citizens, i.e. distinct subsets of stakeholders. These subsets are currently available from the About page via the option “What is ARIADNEplus” as shown:

Figure 3. The “About” Landing page featuring a selection of languages indicated by country flags
The Greek version is shown to the right.

3.2.2 Website Usage Statistics

www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

The Google Analytics Audience Overview report (Fig. 4) provides a high-level view of the number of users who reached the ARIADNEplus website during the first 16 months of project (M2 – M17) since the website was launched in M2.

The site has attracted 10,532 visitors since it was launched, with a total of 31,913 pages viewed. There have been a steady rate of visitors, between 500-1,000 per month with around 14% being return visitors.

Figure 4. Website visitor statistics.

The page/session ratio (Figure 5) shows that the website netted an average of 2.06 pages per visit between M1 and M17. The average session duration (Figure 6) is around two minutes, and the bounce rate (Figure 7) stands at around 59.92%, indicating that 40% of the visitors engage with the site (9esearc. 4,000).

Figure 5. Pages per session.

Figure 6. Average session duration.

Figure 7. Bounce rate.

In terms of page views, (Figure 8) the first place is for website’s homepage, with 12,388 views. The following most visited pages are about the project’s description (/about-ariadne, /portal, /partners, /community, /transnational-access, /resources), this confirms visitors are very much interested in the output of the project and who is involved.

Page	Pageviews	Unique Pageviews	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances	Bounce Rate	% Exit	Page Value
	31,913 % of Total: 100.00% (31,913)	26,442 % of Total: 100.00% (26,442)	00:01:52 Avg for View: 00:01:52 (0.00%)	15,471 % of Total: 100.00% (15,471)	59.92% Avg for View: 59.92% (0.00%)	48.48% Avg for View: 48.48% (0.00%)	\$0.00 % of Total: 0.00% (\$0.00)
1. /	12,388 (38.82%)	10,017 (37.88%)	00:01:50	9,537 (61.64%)	52.33%	50.09%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. /about-ariadne/	3,072 (9.63%)	2,491 (9.42%)	00:02:22	484 (3.13%)	63.64%	45.08%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. /portal/	2,961 (9.28%)	2,534 (9.58%)	00:02:31	842 (5.44%)	73.04%	62.95%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. /partners/	1,879 (5.89%)	1,629 (6.16%)	00:01:47	234 (1.51%)	66.24%	39.97%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
5. /community/	902 (2.83%)	782 (2.96%)	00:00:53	83 (0.54%)	73.49%	24.28%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
6. /transnational-access/	839 (2.63%)	715 (2.70%)	00:02:07	522 (3.37%)	70.69%	58.16%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
7. /resources/	701 (2.20%)	591 (2.24%)	00:00:59	99 (0.64%)	66.67%	27.25%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
8. /category/news/	656 (2.06%)	503 (1.90%)	00:01:17	76 (0.49%)	56.58%	20.73%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
9. /Portal/	504 (1.58%)	495 (1.87%)	00:02:12	469 (3.03%)	88.49%	88.49%	\$0.00 (0.00%)
10. /category/events/	503 (1.58%)	398 (1.51%)	00:00:53	35 (0.23%)	54.29%	18.09%	\$0.00 (0.00%)

Figure 8. Page views.

The user engagement funnel (Figure 9) shows how users navigate the contents of the website.

Figure 9. User navigation paths through the website.

The Acquisition Overview report (Figure 10) shows the percentage of traffic by source.

Figure 10. Website traffic by source.

“Organic Search” (visitors that find the website through a search engine) stands at 39.9%, “Direct” (when the source is unknown, including users that type the website URL directly into their browser, or who bookmark the site) at 37.2%, “Referral” and “Social” at 16.7% and 6.2% respectively.

The Referrals diagram (Figure 11) show the websites that “referred” visitors to the ARIADNEplus website by clicking a link (within another website for example). The highest number of referral links are from the social networks Twitter (“t.co”) and Facebook mobile (“m.facebook.com”), and then from ariadne2.isti.cnr.it.

Source	Acquisition		
	Users	New Users	Sessions
	2,323 % of Total: 22.06% (10,532)	2,069 % of Total: 19.52% (10,602)	3,365 % of Total: 21.75% (15,471)
1. l.co	308 (12.75%)	272 (13.15%)	469 (13.94%)
2. m.facebook.com	200 (8.28%)	200 (9.67%)	211 (6.27%)
3. ariadne2.isti.cnr.it	197 (8.16%)	85 (4.11%)	313 (9.30%)
4. facebook.com	94 (3.89%)	86 (4.16%)	273 (8.11%)
5. e-rihs.eu	87 (3.60%)	87 (4.20%)	99 (2.94%)
6. ariadne-portal.dcu.gr	85 (3.52%)	82 (3.96%)	99 (2.94%)
7. archaeologydataservice.ac.uk	78 (3.23%)	73 (3.53%)	94 (2.79%)
8. inrap.fr	72 (2.98%)	65 (3.14%)	88 (2.62%)
9. cidoc-crm.org	70 (2.90%)	63 (3.04%)	76 (2.26%)
10. ec.europa.eu	58 (2.40%)	54 (2.61%)	62 (1.84%)

Figure 11. Referral sources.

Source 5 is E-RIHS.eu, the RI for Heritage Science, which is an important sub-domain for many archaeologists, and Source 9 is cidoc-crm.org, the established information model used by the project and many other cultural heritage applications.

3.2.2.1 The individual translated sub-pages (*whatis.ariadne-infrastructure.eu*)

The Google Analytics Audience Overview report (Figure 12) and the Pageviews report (Figure 13) covers the period from 1st October 2019 to 31 May 2020. Interest in these pages started to pick up in March 2020 – it is possible that access was not as prominent as it could have been and a non-native English speaker starting at the Home page, may not have realised information was available in their native language. This issue is being addressed in the redesign of the website (c.f. section 4.1).

Figure 12. Page views for the individual language sub-sites.

These statistics are based on the origin of the IP address of the visitor and the language associated with the country registered to it. Whilst English is the most used language at 40%, Italian comes in at 30% and it appears that there have also been a few visitors from Bulgaria, the Czech Republic – and also Japan. It is anticipated that this informative site will be more visited as the project progresses and is better known among stakeholders and the public.

Figure 13. Translated pages viewing figures.

The Google Analytics Audience Overview report (Figure 13) again demonstrates that English and Italian are the dominant page translations viewed although Bulgarian also is around the fifth most viewed language.

3.3 The ARIADNEplus Twitter account

At the end of the ARIADNE project, the associated Twitter account @ARIADNE_Network had about 900 followers, with a few additions during the period between the two project phases. The ARIADNEplus project used the same Twitter account by modifying the profile reference in @ARIADNEplus, in order to maintain continuity with the old project and to keep the existing followers. The profile was reactivated at the end of January 2019. From the end of January to the end of May 2020, the number of followers grew to 1,727 users at the 1st June 2020, a substantial increase.

The following table summarises the monthly activity for the ARIADNEplus Twitter account. It can be seen that on average, there were four Tweets per month with an average of 12,754 views per month and a gain of 48 new followers per month.

Table 1. Twitter statistics.

Month	No. of Tweets	Views	Profile visitors	Mentions	New followers
May-20	1	10,800	171	24	31
Apr-20	24	39,900	330	25	36
Mar-20	1	4,730	102	11	14
Feb-20	1	5,744	62	7	6
Jan-20	4	8,976	138	14	13
Dec-19	1	8,220	147	11	25
Nov-19	4	8,889	508	26	104
Oct-19	3	14,300	201	33	44
Sep-19	8	12,500	321	44	39
Aug-19	1	3,957	49	6	7
Jul-19	0	6,250	281	11	23
Jun-19	5	17,800	501	11	22
May-19	12	15,000	492	17	23
Apr-19	3	5,340	343	24	33
Mar-19	1	4,710	320	6	37
Feb-19	0	36,300	14	0	187
Jan-19	0	13,400	0	0	173
Total	69	216,816	3980	270	817
Average pcm	4	12,754	234	16	48

The most popular Tweet during this period was in June 2019 when researchers were invited to take part in the Community Needs Survey³. This tweet received 8,244 views.

Figure 14. Most popular tweet from the last 17 months.

³ The figure text is in Italian as the statistics automatically adapt the text to the individual user's language of the person who is in charge of the Twitter account.

3.4 Slideshare

Several presentations and reports have been uploaded to the “ariadnenetwork” account. These are summarised in the following table. Whilst the numbers are small in comparison to website visitors, say, this is a supplementary channel that enables promotion of the project to a very wide audience who are looking for specific topics of interest. For example, someone looking for information on the FAIR Data Principles would not be directed to the ARIADNEplus website in the search results but would be exposed to the project via the first presentation in the list below.

Table 2. Slideshare statistics.

Title	Date uploaded	Number of views
“Preferred Formats = Pre-FAIRed Formats” – presentation from FAIR Workshop	M16	56
“Archaeological small finds from field to file: Citizen science approach and data-structure of the PAN project” – presentation from FAIR Workshop	M16	26
D6.1 Initial report on the Innovation Strategy and Targeted Activities	M15	3
ARIADNEplus Community Needs Survey – Key Results	M12	11
ARIADNEplus Community Needs Survey (full report)	M12	22
Czech Archaeology in the Digital Environment – Digitizing Archaeological agenda In Theory and Practice	M6	48
Openarcho – Semantic web platform for interoperable archaeological data	M6	22
ARIADNE at Inrap: Inception, implementation & future	M6	32
My data manager is a robot! Mass ingests and migrations & network integrations	M6	32
Where is the data?	M6	13
Digital Infrastructures for Archaeology: Past, Present and Future Directions	M6	30
Total		295

3.5 Promotional materials

Promotional materials were produced for the project during M1 and M2.

3.5.1 Project logo

The original project logo, which is very distinctive, has been updated for the new project:

Figure 15. The updated ARIADNEplus logo.

3.5.2 Promotional items

For the kick-off meeting in Prato (February 11th-14th, 2019) a kit was created for the participants, featuring the ARIADNEplus logo.

Figure 16. Range of promotional items.

The kit included:

- an aluminium pencil and pen;
- a pad of 'Post-it' notes;
- a notepad with squared paper;
- a backpack bag;
- a meeting badge.

For the badge, a card was designed personalised with the name, surname and the affiliation of the participant. This card can be used for conference and also for luggage. PIN also provided the agenda, internet information and a card image explanation for the badge in the kit bag.

Figure 17. Kick-off meeting documentation and re-usable badge instructions.

Figure 18. ARIADNEplus roll-up posters of the logo.

In addition, two roll-up logo posters were produced for the kick-off meeting – these can be taken and used at future events. For example, at booths at conferences such as EAA and CAA (years 3 & 4).

3.6 Communication and dissemination activities

3.6.1 Project newsletter

Four issues of the project newsletter were published, with the fifth due at the end of June 2020. MailChimp is the tool used to create and distribute the newsletters. The newsletters highlight articles and items from the website with the purpose of allowing recipients access at a click to items of interest to them, whilst also bringing ARIADNEplus to their attention on a regular basis. The Newsletters are distributed via an email list and notices about the newsletter are posted on Twitter. Initially, the Newsletter was distributed to the project participants who are encouraged to forward them to colleagues and other stakeholders. External readers can sign up via the website to be added to the mailing list. The motivation behind publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles is to send traffic to the project website. The first newsletter was sent out in May, after the CAA meeting with subsequent ones published on a 3-monthly basis. The campaign statistics are as follows:

Table 3. Newsletter statistics.

Newsletter No.	No. of subscribers	No. of opens	No. of clicks on links
1	156	70 (46.4%)	13 (8.6%)
2	171	79 (46.2%)	23 (13.5%)
3	178	70 (39.8%)	13 (7.4%)
4	183	76 (41.8%)	17 (9.3%)

On average, each Newsletter was opened by around 75 people (over 40%) with a click-through rate of around 10%. The current subscriber list stands at 187.

3.6.2 Project leaflets

PIN and MiBACT-ICCU have already produced two leaflets, providing information about ARIADNEplus, which are targeted at specific stakeholder communities, researchers and heritage managers.

Figure 19. Leaflet targeted at the research community.

ARIADNEplus
Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Data Networking in Europe

The Project
ARIADNEplus is the continuation of the successful ARIADNE project (2013-2017) for the integration of European archaeological repositories, which created a searchable catalogue of datasets including unpublished reports, images, maps, databases and other kinds of archaeological information accessible online.

The Aim
The project does not aggregate or move data, but only the metadata of the datasets, which are maintained and controlled by their owners. At present, about two million datasets have been catalogued, corresponding to a huge amount of information as each dataset may comprise, for example, an entire report with related images, drawings, or a complete database including thousands of individual records. The catalogued content types range from individual finds to monuments and sites inventories and from the report of one single intervention to the results of a long-term archaeological mission. ARIADNEplus will update existing data in the ARIADNE Portal, extend ARIADNE in geographic and temporal coverage, and in the range of topics addressed, now incorporating additional information about scientific analyses. It will also provide services to further process and re-use these data.

The Catalogue
The ARIADNE catalogue is searchable according to the three facets of "when" (time), "where" (space), "what" (object) and keywords drawn from controlled vocabularies. Searching provides a list of the datasets corresponding to the selection criteria with summary information about their content and a link to the source data, which can thus be accessed by the user according to the rules established by the content owner.

Partners
The 41 ARIADNEplus partners came from 23 European countries, plus 4 international partners. ARIADNEplus is funded in support researchers; but we believe it may be important and useful also for heritage agencies and managers.

Policies and strategies
The ARIADNEplus work plan includes a group of activities dedicated to documenting and proposing relevant policies and strategies for data such as the application of the FAIR principles and the certification of repositories. It will also address some fundamental issues, for example developing guidelines for the creation, management and sustainability of archaeological repositories. There is a European crisis in physical repositories, and a pressing need for guidelines for physical archives, but it is equally important that digital archives are recognised. Such documents may be of particular interest to heritage managers, policy makers and their agencies. Moreover, our activity on policies and strategies includes provision for training for users, researchers and managers alike. To facilitate serving the different communities targeted by these activities, it is planned that the support material, initially prepared in English, will be translated in various EU languages. Such localization will also take into account local regulations and the diverse needs of stakeholders. In general, the scope of the ARIADNEplus policies and strategies activities is not restricted to research; if there is a specific interest, they can include subjects more related to other areas, such as data for heritage management and site conservation.

Technology
Although most of the technology employed in ARIADNEplus concerns the data integration goals of the project, including the creation of a searchable catalogue and the development of a Linked Open Data approach, a key role is played by the data services which the project will make available. These range from tools for data analysis (e.g. for data mining and Natural Language Processing) and for data synthesis, (e.g. visualization of images and 3D, locating data on a map or in time, browsing the data using Linked Open Data, and so on). We will also develop a number of pilot applications, to demonstrate service usage in exemplary cases. While unplanned additional services might probably be limited only to extensions of the planned ones, there is ample space for choosing pilot applications which match the needs of heritage managers.

Networking and training
Consolidating a comprehensive, active and informed community is one of the goals of the ARIADNEplus project, which envisages a large number of initiatives, such as workshops, sessions at events, meetings and dedicated communication channels. Particular attention will be dedicated to regions or countries where archaeological dataset creation, processing and management may be less advanced compared to the others: a working group on Central and Southern Europe has already been set up. A similar approach will target groups defined according to their specific needs, for example museums, archaeological sites, and so on; the same will apply to different roles in cultural heritage and archaeology, such as site managers, museum curators, investigators and researchers, teachers, and communicators. Many of the networking activities include a substantial training component, with the provision of training material both for direct participation, e.g. documentation and guidelines, and for remote participation, e.g. webinars. The ARIADNEplus training plan also envisages specific training activities. These include tutorials and training workshops as well as knowledge transfer actions on individual projects, in which a small team is directly supported by ARIADNEplus experts.

Contact us
ARIADNEplus is keen to get in touch with potential users and listen to their needs, addressing them within the project whenever possible.

You may contact the project coordinator
Francis Niccolucci directly at: coordinator@ariadne-infrastructure.eu

He will direct you to the most appropriate partners in charge of the activity or activities that better correspond to your request. Updated news are available from the web site and from our social accounts.

Further information is available on the web site:
www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

ARIADNEplus is a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon programme. Contract No. 101019745-RISE-01. 2014-2020.

Figure 20. Leaflet targeted at Heritage Managers.

Project partners are encouraged to provide translations if this is appropriate for their countries.

3.6.3 Other dissemination materials

A basic set of promotional materials was also prepared and made available for use. These materials include:

- a set of project logos for use in printed materials and online resources, with branding guidelines and instructions for printers;
- templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.;
- a project description sheet (condensed version from the DoW [3]);
- an ARIADNEplus Essentials PowerPoint presentation.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the ARIADNE project VRE on D4Science. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by partners.

The planned new project poster has been deferred until the Portal is sufficiently updated with new data and services since the current poster (from ARIADNE) is still relevant as there are no physical events taking place.

3.7 Dissemination and communication activities

3.7.1 Events

This Task concerns the planning of regular dissemination and communication events aimed at increasing awareness about ARIADNEplus, showcasing project achievements and fostering the meeting of the ARIADNEplus community with stakeholders. Such events are generally co-located with major conferences and symposia and planned according to favourable opportunities. The first such event was the project kick-off meeting which was organised by PIN and held at Prato, Italy from 11th-14th February. During the four days, participants were introduced to the aims of the project, sessions were provided on key topics to bring the new partners (i.e. who were not in the original ARIADNE project) up to speed and the special interest groups (SIGs) met for the first time. A full report is available on the website at: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/ariadneplus-kick-off-meeting-report/>.

For ARIADNEplus, there are two major archaeology conferences, EAA and CAA, which are of key importance to the project. In general, the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) annual conference should be where the annual ARIADNEplus General assembly will be held, as many partners will be present for this conference. The EAA represents the main body of European archaeologists, and has had over 11,000 members from 60 countries worldwide working in prehistory, classical, medieval and later archaeology. The EAA also sets professional and ethical standards for archaeological work. CAA (Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology) and CHNT (Cultural Heritage and New Technologies) are organisations for the more digitally inclined archaeologists, each representing smaller communities, but still a main target group for ARIADNEplus activities. In 2020, the organization of the two Conferences has been disrupted by the COVID-19 emergency and virtual substitutes are being planned.

In the reporting period M1-M18, we have focused on the following types of events:

- Dedicated project sessions
- Partner's individual presentations
- Virtual individual presentations (since March 2020)

Major archaeology conferences were the platform for ARIADNEplus events. The highlight was a session at the CAA 2019 in Krakow, bringing former and new project partners, as well as external projects together to reflect on the direction of development for research infrastructures in archaeology. The event subsequently led to a publication of results in the 'The ARIADNE Impact' book (Niccolucci and Richards 2019). Many events were dedicated to the introduction of the new ARIADNEplus project to national and international archaeological and digital communities through individual project partners (c.f. the table "Events" for full list of events).

Many of the partners have attended and promoted the project at local/national archaeological events across Europe.

In April 2019, Arizona State University had a booth at the Society for American Archaeology 2019 Annual meeting in the USA, and a Workshop was organised at DH2019 in Utrecht in July, one of the key Conferences for the Digital Humanities in Europe. The project was also well represented in several sessions at EAA in Bern, Switzerland in September 2019, and at the Europeana Conference in Lisbon in the same month. A joint round table was organised with SEADDA at CHNT in November in Vienna. In January 2020, Julian Richards attended the Society Historical Archaeology (SHA) annual conference in Boston and in February Ceri Binding from the University of South Wales contributed to the Getty International Terminology Working Group Meeting in Los Angeles.

ARIADNEplus also participated in two virtual events. In April 2020, ARIADNEplus was represented (by Achille Felicetti, PIN) at a Twitter Conference “DH in the Time of Virus” (see illustration below) and then on the 27th May, Franco Niccolucci (PIN) represented the project at the “European web conference on 3D digital cultural heritage for resilience, recovery and sustainability” which was streamed via YouTube and organised by ARIADNEplus, in conjunction with Inception spin-off (a spin-off company born from the INCEPTION Eu project, <https://www.inceptionspinoff.com/en/inception-spinoff/>)) and the European Commission, DG CONNECT, Unit G.2 – Interactive Technologies, Digital for Culture & Education. To date, this has had 2,784 views on YouTube.

Figure 21. Tweet about DH in the Time of Virus.

The CAA Conference, which was due to take place in Oxford, UK from 14-17 April 2020 has been postponed and eventually cancelled due to the pandemic. ARIADNEplus had two potential roundtable discussions accepted, but these were not able to go forward. CAA plans to go ahead with a meeting in 2021 in Limassol, Cyprus. The EAA Conference which was to take place from 24-30 August 2020 in will now be held as a virtual event over the same period, and the joint ARIADNEplus/SEADDA session will go ahead.

In the next project period, ARIADNEplus will additionally be present with booths to disseminate new outputs, information and training materials, and make personal contact with the archaeological community at the major conferences (provided travel restrictions are lifted).

Table 4. Events

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
2019								
March 13-14	COST Connect Sharing is Caring? Data sharing in the context of networks in science and technology	Brussels, Belgium	No	G.Pálsson (FI), Hella Hollander (DANS): everybody attending giving a short presentation	Yes	Archiving institutes, researchers, engineers, private industry, policy makers	35	
March 26	OEAW Internal Networking Meeting of digital archaeologists	Vienna, Austria	Yes (OEAW)	E.Aspöck (ÖAW), introduction of ARIADNEplus as part of discussion	No	Digital archaeologists data managers, DH specialists	10	
March 30	Protection of Cultural Heritage in Greece: Digital challenges	Athens, Greece	No	K. Kotsakis (AUTH) – [dataset provider], M. Katsianis (PP), presentation on dataset, mentioning of A	No	Archaeologists Academia	c.50	
April 3-4	Slovenski arheološki dnevi	Ljubljana, Slovenia	No	B.Štular (ZRC SAZU), presenting the ARIADNEplus project to Slovenian archaeologists	No	Archaeologists	c. 70	
April 10-13	Society for American Archaeology 2019 Annual meeting	Albuquerque, New Mexico, USA	No	Booth (ARIADNE + handouts), R.Fernandez (ASU)	Yes	Archaeologists	c. 50	

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
April 23-27	CAA 2019	Kraków, Poland	Yes	Session organised by J.Richards & H.Wright (ADS) Presentations by V.Glissen (DANS), O.Marlet & X.Rodier (CNRS), B. Štular (ZRC SAZU), J.Hasil,D.Novak (ARUP-CAS), A.Kaneda (NARA), Kai Rossenbach Salas and A. Marx (Inrap), G Palson (FI); N. Kecheva (NIAM-BAS); Aspöck , Hiebel (OEAW);	Yes	Archaeologists	50	Publication of book 'The ARIADNE impact' (Niccolucci and Richards, 2019)
May 2-4	The 8 th Joint Meeting of ECFN and nomisma.org 2019 – http://nomisma.org-ecfn2019.unime.it/	Messina, Italy	Yes (RGK)	D.Wigg-Wolf (RGK)	Yes	Numismatists, IT developers, digital numismatists	60	Increased awareness of ARIADNE+ among the digital numismatic community
May 13	ArchAIDE final conference	Pisa, Italy	No	J. Richards (ADS) – presentation on Open Data, introducing role of ARIADNEplus	Yes	Archaeologists	60	

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	Internal?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
May 25-29	DHD 2019	Frankfurt am Main, Germany	No	D.Wigg-Wolf (RGK)	Yes	Digital humanists	c. 40	
May 29-31	CAA-CZ/SK 2019	Kočovce, Slovakia	No	Presentation: D.Novák (ARUP-CAS)	Yes	Digital archaeologists	c. 100	
June 5-7	International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies (ACIT) 2019, https://acit.tneu.edu.ua/	České Budějovice, Czechia	No	Presentation: D.Novák (ARUP-CAS) & O.Lečbychová (ARUB-CAS)	Yes	Computer scientists, software engineers	c. 20	
July 9-12	DH2019	Utrecht, Netherlands	Yes, organised a workshop (CNRS)	Workshop and presentations by A.Joffre, O.Marlet, X.Rodier (CNRS)	Yes	Digital archaeologists, digital humanists		
July 15-19	XX Argentine National Archaeology Congress (https://ffyh.unc.edu.ar/eventos/xx-congreso-nacional-de-arqueologia-argentina/)	Córdoba, Argentina	Yes (CONICET)	A.Izeta, R.Cattáneo (CONICET), presenting Round Table: Red Nacional de Arqueología Digital... ¿por qué y para qué? (National Network of Digital Archaeology ... Why and for what?)	No	Archaeologists		

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
Sept. 12	19 th European Networked Organization Systems (NKOS) Workshop, part of TPDL (https://nkos-eu.github.io/2019/programme.html)	Oslo, Norway	Yes (USW Hypermedia Group)	Presentation D. Tudhope	Yes	Digital librarians, resource discovery service providers, KOS developers and LAM professionals	16	presented on multilingual vocabulary mapping work
Sept. 4-7	EAA 2019 (https://www.eaa.org/eea2019)	Bern, Switzerland	Yes, session organised by RGK, USW	Presentations from partners in several digital archaeology sessions (e.g. 322, by ADS and PIN) and organisation of session 175 on RESEARCH DATA AND DIGITAL CORPORA (co-organisers include Wigg-Wolf and May)	Yes	Archaeologists, digital archaeologists, data managers	c.30	
Sept. 27-29	Europeana Conference 2019	Lisbon, Portugal	Yes (ICCU, Sara Di Giorgio)	Workshop: European Open Science Cloud, presentation "The ARIADNE cloud" with Franco Niccolucci	Yes	Cultural heritage and digital humanities	40	

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	Internal?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
Sept. 27-29	Europeana Conference 2019	Lisbon, Portugal	Yes (CARARE, Kate Fernie)	Workshop: 3D Task Force, presentation “3D models in the ARIADNE repository” by Franco Niccolucci	Yes	Cultural heritage and digital humanities	25	Ongoing work on 3D interoperability
Sept. 27-29	Europeana Conference 2019	Lisbon, Portugal	Yes (ICCU, Sara Di Giorgio)	Workshop: How to Implement the FAIR Principles in Digital Culture, presentation “FAIR principles implementation within ARIADNE” with Franco Niccolucci	Yes	Cultural heritage and digital humanities	40	
Oct. 3-5	COST-ARKWORK conference: On shifting grounds – the study of archaeological practices in a changing world.	Rethymno, Crete	Yes (ARKWORK)	M. Katsianis (PP), K. Kotsakis – [dataset provider], F. Stefanou (AUTH), presentation on “Remediating the excavation archive”	Yes	Archaeologists, data managers, DH specialists, anthropologists, archaeological ethnographers	c.50	Feedback on research as part of A+
Nov. 4-6	CHNT’24 – International Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies, (http://www.chnt.at/)	Vienna, Austria	Yes, A+ & SEADDA roundtable “FAIR Archaeology” (ADS & OEAW & SRFG)	Presentations by A.Felicetti (PIN), G.Geser (SRFG), F.Niccolucci (PIN), J.Richards (ADS)	Yes	Archaeologists	15	Papers by A+ presenters

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
Nov. 21-22	Masterclass on Open Access Digital Publication	Pisa, Italy	No	J.Richards gave two classes to Univ of Pisa staff and students	No	undergraduate and postgraduate students	30	
Dec. 5	Workshop Materiais históricos: entre tradição e inovação	Lisbon, Portugal	Yes (LNEC)	A. Santos Silva, M. J. Correia, R. Fontinha, M.R. Veiga, D. Costa, M. Menezes	No	Cultural heritage specialists	108	
Dec. 9	RISCAPE – International Research Infrastructure Landscape – Final Event	Brussels, Belgium	No	F.Niccolucci (PIN) presented the perspective of archaeological research infrastructure (ARIADNE), https://riscape.eu/2019/10/17/riscape-international-landscape-report-launch-event/	Yes	Research infrastructure developers/managers	50	ARIADNE is presented in the humanities part of the RISCAPE report
2020								
January 10	Society Historical Archaeology (SHA) annual conference	Boston, USA	No	J. Richards (ADS)	Yes	Archaeologists	12	
January 14	DiSSCo – Distributed System of Scientific Collections workshop	Delft, The Netherlands	No	F.Niccolucci (PIN) – Presentation of ARIADNEplus: Online Humanities Platforms	Yes	Researchers, curators & managers of collections for natural sciences	10	

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
Feb. 6-7	Getty International Terminology Working Group Meeting h(https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/itwg_2020_agenda_participants.pdf)	Getty Centre, Los Angeles	No	Ceri Binding (USW)	Yes	AAT vocabulary advisors, digital librarians	35	Sharing experience from ARIADNEplus vocabulary matching
Feb. 21	Archon Winter School: Sharing Practices: Archaeological 3D Visualisation in the Netherlands	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	No	Valentijn Gilissen (DANS)	Yes	Archaeologists	50	Sharing the needs of 31 researcher in a European perspective
March 5	Seminário Os materiais que constroem o património: conhecer, cuidar e salvar	Lisbon, Portugal	Yes (LNEC)	A. Santos Silva, M.J. Correia, R. Fontinha, D. Costa, M.R. Veiga, L. Nunes, J.M. Mimoso, M. Vieira, M. Menezes	No	Archaeologists, engineers, restorers, decision makers		Postponed – new date to be announced
April 2	#DHgoesVIRAL	Virtual	No	The ARIADNEplus at PIN (Achille Felicetti) presented in this digital humanities focused twitter-based conference the project's approach to data integration	Yes	Digital humanists	150 (estimated)	#DHgoesVIRAL ranking 5 th on Twitter trending in Greece

DATE	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by ARIADNEplus partner? (organisation)	Who gave a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International?	Target Audience (e.g. Archaeologists Software Engineers Decision Makers)	Estimated number of researchers / people reached	Outcomes (feedback, results...)
April 3	Italian workshop on 3D for cultural heritage and archaeology	Virtual	Co-organizer	Presentations by Franco Niccolucci, Achille Felicetti and Paola Ronzino	No	Archaeologists, architects, heritage professionals	300	Network of interested stakeholders established
May 27	European web conference on 3D digital cultural heritage for resilience, recovery and sustainability	Virtual	Yes (PIN, Franco Niccolucci)	F.Niccolucci (PIN), Sorin Hermon (CYI) and Kate Fernie (CARARE) – present online.	Yes	Policy makers, researchers, industry stakeholders	2,784 views on YouTube	

Postponed Events (2020)

DATE planned	Event Title (and URL if available)	Town, Country	Event or part of it (co-) organised by A+ partner? (organiser)	Who was planned to give a presentation on or mentioned ARIADNEplus (name, organisation)	International ?	Target Audience (e.g. archaeologists, software engineers, etc.)	Estimated number of participants / people reached
April 14-17	CAA Oxford	Oxford, UK	Yes (ADS)	Cancelled	Yes	Digital archaeologists	
May 12-15	4º Encontro de Conservação e Reabilitação de Edifícios	Lisbon, Portugal - POSTPONED	Yes (LNEC)	A. Santos Silva, M.R. Veiga, L. Nunes, M. Menezes	No	Archaeologists, engineers, restorers, decision makers	400 were registered
May 20-22	GARR Conference “Data and Technologies for the Future”	Rescheduled for 19-21 May 2021	No	PIN will present a paper	No	Technology providers and end users in education and research	200-300

3.7.2 Publications

MiBACT-ICCU leads Task 7.4 which concerns the publication of materials by the project including:

- scientific publications in academic journals;
- training materials;
- service specific brochures and fact sheets;
- project brochures and leaflets.

To date, the project has produced the following publications:

Scientific publications in academic journals

Four papers were published in 2019, the second publication being a collection of papers contributed by several of the partners based upon presentations at CAA, Krakow about the impact of ARIADNE/plus upon the archaeological community.

Table 5. Scientific publications

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2019	ARIADNEplus and community data repositories. Innovative solutions for sharing open archaeological data	CHNT 24 - International Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies, Vienna, 2019	Geser, Guntram (Salzburg Research)	Researchers and practitioners in digital repositories and research infrastructures	150
	URL	https://www.chnt.at/wp-content/uploads/ARIADNEplus-and-community-data-repositories.pdf			
2019	The ARIADNE Impact (book of 17 papers – hard copy and PDF)	Richards J. & Niccolucci F. (eds.): The ARIADNE Impact. Budapest: Archaeolingua	Various authors from ARIADNEplus	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	700 (Zenodo: 550 downloads, 789 views)
	URL	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3476712			
2019	The ARIADNEplus program integrating European archaeological datasets was launched	Hungarian Archaeology E-Journal 2019 Spring	Attila Kreiter (Hungarian National Museum)	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	1,500
	URL	http://www.hungarianarchaeology.hu/?page_id=8019			
2019	Elindult az európai régészeti adatbázisokat integráló ARIADNEplus program	Magyar Régészet Online Magazin 2019 tavasz	Attila Kreiter (Hungarian National Museum)	Researchers and practitioners in digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	1,500

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
	URL	http://www.magyarregeszet.hu/?page_id=11954/			
2019	Moving towards an open archaeology: projects, opportunities and challenges	Mitteilungen der Vereinigung Österreichischer Bibliothekarinnen und Bibliothekare, 72(2), S. 538-554. doi: 10.31263/voebm.v72i2.3249.	Edeltraud Aspöck, OEAW	Open Science community, Librarians, Digital Humanist	72 downloads since Nov. 2019 - 500
	URL	https://journals.univie.ac.at/index.php/voebm/article/view/3249/			

In addition, ARIADNEplus has been referred in the following papers (acknowledging EC support):

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2019	The Archaeological Information System of the Czech Republic - A Big Solution for Big Data	Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies 2018	Novák, David (Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic)	All of the above.	30 views (06-06-2020)
	URL	https://www.academia.edu/41545692/The_Archaeological_Information_System_of_the_Czech_Republic_-_A_Big_Solution_for_Big_Data			
2019	IT and the Humanities in the 21st Century - The Case for Archaeology	9th International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies Conference Proceedings	Novák, David (Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic)	All of the above.	48 views 906-06-2020)
	URL	https://www.academia.edu/39392921/IT_and_the_Humanities_in_the_21_st_Century_-_The_Case_for_Archaeology			

The following articles have been submitted earlier this year for publication:

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2020	Re-mediating the excavation archive	Article submitted in Journal of Anthropological and Archaeological Sciences	Markos Katsianis (University of Patras) Kostas Kotsakis (Aristotle University Thessaloniki) Filippos Stefanou (Aristotle University Thessaloniki)	Researchers and practitioners in archaeological excavation research, digital archaeology, cultural heritage, and research infrastructures	N/A

Date	Title of Article/Paper	Publication	Authors & organisation	Type of Audience e.g. archaeologists, researchers, data managers etc.	Estimated reach
2020	Bunkers from the Second World War on the Black Sea coast, Romania: an archaeological essay	A collective book, papers in honour of Prof. Monica Mărgineanu Cârstoiu	Alexandru Dragoman (The Vasile Pârvan Institute of Archaeology)	Archaeologists	N/A

Training materials

No specific training materials were created during the first period for public consumption, as the Portal was not yet ready. However, an internal manual, *The Aggregation Pipeline User Guide*, was written and is updated as progress is made with the mapping of data, and the project partners submit their data for ingest into the ARIADNEplus portal. The current version is 1.9 (May 2020) and this will be made available (via the Training Hub) once the aggregation has stabilised and the Portal is accepting third party metadata. Two of the presentations from the virtual training workshop on FAIR Data Management will be available via the Training Hub when this is launched this summer.

Service specific brochures and fact sheets

These will be created as the first of the new services become available for use.

Project brochures and leaflets

Two brochures were produced at the beginning of the project as described in section 3.6.2.

3.8 Transnational Access and Training

3.8.1 Transnational access

Transnational access (TNA) provides focussed training, predominantly for young researchers, and is often their first experience of working with a research infrastructure. There are three providers in ARIADNEplus who offer TNA as follows:

- PIN VASTLab offers one-week in-house training courses tailored to single or groups of users who need to develop their archaeological datasets and improve their interoperability, using standards such as CIDOC-CRM and the infrastructure tools and services;
- UoY-ADS, as an accredited archaeological data repository, specialise in data management and stewardship and offer in-house visits, usually of around three days duration, to users needing guidance and support with this topic;
- CNR-ISTI is devoted to ICT research and provides expertise in the design of archaeological datasets and thesauri. In-house visits are offered to users requiring support with the creation, access and integration of such datasets with full access to facilities such as computers and tools. The VCL laboratory specialises in 3D data acquisition and management and offers in-house training with full use of its visual media tools. This type of training is offered as a five-day summer school.

The first call for in-house training at PIN and ADS, was published in September and posted on the project social media channels as well as the website. In addition, the call was also posted in a number of Facebook and LinkedIn Archaeology-related groups. Partners were also requested to promote the call through their own communications, and this proved to be the most fruitful method for attracting applicants. The first round of individual placements was well received, attracting 16 applicants of which 13 received offers. Four students were able to complete their training at PIN and ADS prior to the COVID-19 travel restrictions and the remaining candidates have had their training places held until it is possible to travel once again. The planned Summer Schools at CNR had to be cancelled. These will be rescheduled for 2021 as difficulties are still anticipated with travel up to the end of the year.

3.8.2 Training

Activities under this task concern the planning of short training events, usually organised during important events for potential users of the ARIADNEplus services. They may consist in generic tutorials or short hands-on demonstrations of individual services. They will also create good promotional opportunities to advertise the use of ARIADNEplus services. The task also includes planning the creation of training webinars or video tutorials to be published on the web site, possibly adapting existing training material. This training task will complement the training activity produced by TNA, which will be based on individual participation and longer duration. Due to the nature the training activity, it could not take place in M1-M12, as other tasks must be finished before training can take place. However, these other tasks will be monitored closely and appropriate training events discussed and planned within the WP and by the task leaders involved as opportunities arise. These may be training workshops held at key conferences (assuming acceptance of proposals) or may be organised locally by partners for their specific national communities. ZRC SAZU will be in charge of planning the training; PIN(PRISMA) will manage the technical production of webinars or video tutorials; all partners will be involved as possible trainers, or as training event organisers.

One planned training event was scheduled for M15 – a workshop on FAIR Data Management and Trust Concepts and Standards, organised by WP3 for the project partners. The event was to take place from 16-18 March in The Hague and Leiden, The Netherlands. As the physical meeting proved impossible, the workshop became a virtual event which was held on the 17th March instead and focussed upon the FAIR Data Management only. In total, there were 42 participants.

The FAIR Data Management workshop programme consisted of three one-hour lectures as follows:

- Herbert Van de Sompel kicked the meeting off with his lecture on *An Institutional Perspective to Rescue Scholarly Orphans*. In the Scholarly Orphans project, funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the team looked into archiving artifacts (presentations, code, data, etc.) that researchers deposit in various web platforms (GitHub, Slideshare, Zenodo, personal websites, etc.), but that go unnoticed by their institutions.
- The second speaker, Valentijn Gilissen, gave a presentation entitled *Preferred Formats = Pre-FAIRed formats* where he explained the reasoning behind DANS's preferred formats policy and demonstrated how such a policy contributes to producing FAIR data. In short, DANS considers that the file formats best suited for long-time preservation and accessibility are file formats which are commonly used, have open specifications, and are independent of specific software, developers or suppliers.
- Last but not least, Stijn Heeren presented the Portable Antiquities of the Netherlands (PAN) project in his lecture *Archaeological small finds from field to file: Citizen science approach and data structure of the PAN-project*. Stijn emphasized the role of private finders contributing to the project. In addition, he discussed the PAN portal and the data model behind the description of the findings in detail, and how this approach leads to publishing data that is FAIR .

3.9 Monitoring and assessment

The dissemination programme is monitored and assessed to review:

- **what messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them;**
- **whether those messages are being understood and remembered;**
- **whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.**

This information will help in planning subsequent phases of the marketing strategy, in developing future marketing activities and in order to make revisions of this marketing strategy plan. It will ensure that the marketing strategy is effectively reaching the target audiences and they are acting on the messages they receive.

Success indicators:

- stakeholder involvement;
- number of institutional stakeholders involved e.g. by becoming associates, participating in bilateral meetings, sending researchers to participate in TNA and training events, taking part in user surveys and other activities;
- user involvement;
- number of users participating in project training activities, attending workshops and presentations etc.;
- project website developed;
- number of unique visitors;
- research infrastructure online services;
- number of unique users;

- number of ARIADNEplus Twitter followers, reach (number of people who see messages and retweets);
- number of people reached via other media channels e.g. newspapers, YouTube, interviews;
- number of presentations at relevant conferences and events;
- number of presentations and project publications downloaded from Slideshare;
- number of readers of ARIADNEplus email newsletter.

The following figures have been produced by looking at the numbers achieved by ARIADNE as reported in the final Dissemination report [3], using these as guidelines to obtain realistic targets.

Table 6: Indicators to be used for monitoring the dissemination impact.

Description	Measure	Month 18 Target	Month 18 Actual	Comments
Stakeholder involvement	Number of institutions	50	>150	Survey (150) + Associate partner ROCEEH + Event workshops
User involvement	Number of participants	1,000	>1,000	E.g. 700 survey respondents, 789 downloads of Impact booklet, event attendees
Project website	Visitors	10,000	10,532	
Research infrastructure online services (Portal)	Anonymous users	5,000	2,580	Actual figures Apr 2019 – May 2020 + estimates for other 4 months.
Social networks (Twitter)	Number of members	1,500	1,727	
Social networks (Twitter)	Number of people reached	5,000	>8,000	Av. per Tweet is 3,142 and max. is 8,244.
Communication via other channels	Number of people reached	1,000	>1,000	Zenodo 789, Facebook 20, Newspapers 100+, Partner social media & newsletters etc.
Presentations at international events	Number of people reached	100	>500	Total audience = 1,206 but will include some double+ counting.
Downloads from Slideshare	Number of people reached	500	295	This figure will improve as more content is uploaded.
Newsletters	Number of readers	100	~75 actual readers	187 subscribers, 70-79 opened.

At M18, most of the indicator targets have been met or exceeded. The Slideshare download figures are on the low side but there are not a lot of new resources uploaded yet, plus the Impact publication is not available on Slideshare but via Zenodo. Since the latter has been downloaded 789 times to date from Zenodo, the two figures combined easily exceed the target of 500. The newsletter target has also been missed but an open rate of 40% is very good so this is an effective communication channel which probably needs better promotion on the website.

Figure 22. ARIADNE Portal users (April 2019 – May 2020).

Finally, an estimated figure of 2,580 visitors to the Portal (ARIADNE Gateway) based upon the following graph and assuming around 75 visitors per month is assumed for January-March 2019 and 225 for June 2020. This figure is only around half of the target, but it is increasing steadily, despite there being no active promotion of the Portal during the first period. This figure should improve as a substantial new body of data is uploaded into the Portal and new tools and services are developed which will enable dissemination and communication during the next period. At present, this work is in progress, with the first datasets just starting to appear in the Portal, and the new services and tools yet to be developed and integrated.

In conclusion, the indicators show that during the first period, ARIADNEplus has been effective at building its community and disseminating information about the project. Promotion of the key output, the updated Portal, has been low-key, and the figures reflect this.

3.10 Recommendations from the Strategic Advisory Board concerning Dissemination and Communication

A number of recommendations were made by the Strategic Advisory Board regarding WP7, which were included in the first report (Appendix 1), many of which have already been taken on board, and at M18, the current status is as follows.

Dissemination

- Network with as many other similar projects with the ARIADNEplus website.
 - this recommendation will be implemented during Period 2, based around the Community section. Networking with other projects has taken place through meetings and events and our new associated members and allies such as SEADDA will be highlighted.
- Besides creating own channels, ARIADNEplus should exploit existing local projects to improve public dissemination. Among others, the following were mentioned:
 - Heritage Information Access Strategy by Historic England, Local Authority Historic Environment Records in England; several liaisons of this type are described in D2.2 Initial Report on Networking and Integration.
 - Hungarian Archaeology Online, a quarterly e-journal, available also in English accessed each month approximately by 10.000 archaeologists and researchers. Paper published by Attila Kreiter of the Hungarian National Museum in 2019.
- Printed materials continue to be a useful means for broadcasting project results. Leaflets or other materials that can be taken away by conference attendees will magnify the project's resonance within the community; leaflets as described in section 3.6.2 were designed for this purpose.
- Print-on-demand: Archaeolingua continues to publish, for example, the EAC's Annual Meetings Extended Abstracts with links to the full online versions of the papers. Libraries and archives request the published paper copies, which are kept for consultation; Archeolingua published the book "The ARIADNE Impact" in 2019 following the successful session at CAA, Krakow.
- Webinars: some of the presentations given during the ARIADNEplus kick-off were excellent and could easily be converted into webinars; webinars are planned for the final period when all the tools and services will be available.
- Media coverage is an aspect that has not been fully developed. Appointing a media expert to follow the project and interact with the media (television, radio, newspapers, and so on) would be of great advantage. Media coverage is also planned for the final period, however, some coverage has already taken place, e.g. NARA.
- Museums: at this stage, the project is involved only with a few museums that have a research section. One of the project's implementation pilots is led by the Moesgaard Museum (MOMU) in Denmark. The pilot can be disseminated through NEMO, the Network of European Museum Organisations.

Conferences

- There are many new fields of research (Bioarchaeology, aDNA, Environmental Studies, and so on) that are unaware of the ARIADNEplus project. The project must therefore increase its presence in specialised conferences/events with the aim of reaching these different academic communities, such as:
 - The Archaeological Museum in Zagreb (AMZ), our partner in the project, together with the EAA organised a conference on archaeology and tourism during the first

week of May 2019; Archaeolingua was present with a session, ARIADNEplus could also get in touch with the organisers and provide materials for dissemination; this conference was attended by Franco Niccolucci of PIN.

- The EAC Annual Symposium is another venue to understand the government angle on what ARIADNEplus is doing. It would be useful to have another symposium, such as the one that took place in Brighton in 2016; to be considered once travel can resume.
- The project needs to be more present at events where computer scientists are involved. This audience is not fully aware of the problems related to the integration of archaeological research, and vice-versa.
 - Partners from ARUP-CAS presented at International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies (ACIT) 2019.
 - PIN was due to present a paper at GARR, the national Italian network provider for the education and research sectors, postponed to next year.
 - CNR was also due to take part in a round table at CAA, postponed to next year.

In summary, the project has already adopted many of the recommendations and will address the remaining suggestions, plus any new recommendations from the SAB, as it progresses.

4 Communication and dissemination plan for M19-M36

The Communication and Dissemination activities will continue to use the website, workshops and conference sessions, social media (i.e. Twitter, Slideshare, Facebook etc.) to promote the ARIADNE infrastructure to its stakeholders. As the work of the project progresses and the outputs begin to develop, it will be possible to focus on specific archaeological sub-domains, as mappings and vocabularies are completed within WP4. Some specific activities planned for Period 2, and which take account of the current situation, are described in this section.

4.1 New design & structure of the website

Following the first period experience with the website and the increasing importance of this communication channel as part of the overall strategy, it was agreed to modify the design and add new content. The following changes are currently being implemented with a planned relaunch for M18. The Homepage and menus of the website have already been updated, and submitted to the partners for feedback.

- Visual impact – many users now use mobile devices rather than desktop screens, with laptops far more dominant than desk top computers. These reduces the amount of visible webpage seen by an end user, and with the previous design, the top-level menu and image were all that was seen, with scrolling required to look at any new content. To improve the visual impact of the website, the logo and top-level menu were consolidated and the layout reorganised so the content is more compact, and immediately visible to the viewer.
- Navigation – the project has four main areas of interest: the ARIADNEplus Community, the project’s ongoing work and outputs, the Portal (i.e. the primary output) and a new section called Training Hub. The content was re-organised around these four main pillars as follows:
 - The ARIADNEplus Community – until now, the Community aspect of the project was relatively low-key but is in reality, one of the most important features of the project. Growing the community, obtaining agreement and buy-in of best practices and standards, and getting feedback on their needs is key to the success and sustainability of the ARIADNE infrastructure. In turn, as a representative RI for archaeology, ARIADNE has an important role for influencing policy and research priorities in Europe and the wider geographical sphere. The new website will put the Community at the forefront and encourage more individuals, organisations and projects to participate. The Community “Join us” page will make the benefits clearer, especially for individuals, and highlight the many different (and new) sub-domains which the new Portal will address.
 - Activities and Resources – this section will include the existing resources (short reports, deliverables etc.) plus some new short videos which will focus on specific aspects of the project (c.f. section 4.4).
 - The Portal – this is the same but is being updated with more data and additional services as planned by the project.
 - The Training Hub – this is a new section which is being added to the website following the feedback from the Community Needs Survey (c.f. section 4.3).
- News and Events – the news items and the Twitter feed are being given a prominent position since this is a key communication channel for the project.

Figure 23 shows the new design for the Home page. Minor edits are expected following partners’ feedback.

Figure 23. The new ARIADNEplus website Home page design.

4.2 The Training Hub

The Community Needs Survey⁴ asked respondents about their training needs for a number of identified topics. The responses strongly indicated an unmet demand across the board as follows:

1. Apply open/FAIR Principles to Archaeology (67.3%)
2. Deposit project datasets in a digital repository (62.8%)
3. Develop data science skills (60.7%)
4. Manage datasets of a large archaeological project (59%)
5. Manage a digital repository of archaeological data (58.8%)
6. Produce metadata for archaeological datasets (57.3%)
7. Define and implement a Data Management Plan (DMP) (55.8%)
8. Use Domain vocabularies to describe datasets (48.5%)

ARIADNEplus has also planned to provide some training in the form of internal workshops for its participants plus two workshops on the FAIR Data Principles in Years 2 and 4. Furthermore, it is anticipated that some sort of training may be required for the new services to be provided by the Portal. For example, an internal manual has already been produced for partners using the Aggregation services – this is updated periodically as new metadata sets are uploaded. Once this task has been completed and the manual finalised, it will be made available as a training resource. Training materials and manuals may also be required for new services to be made available in the Portal. Finally, the project is providing Transnational Access visits and summer schools. All these activities require co-ordination and organisation and the resources to be made available in one place. Consequently, a new “Training Hub” has been created initially in the form of a Directory with ten top-level topics – the eight identified in the Survey plus “Use of the ARIADNE+ Portal (data and services)” and “Working with Research Infrastructures”.

Whilst the project will produce some useful training resources as an output of its planned activities, it does not have the budget to produce a large range of new training resources for all these identified topics. However, some very useful training materials have been produced by other Humanities Research Infrastructures and projects such as DARIAH and PARTHENOS and the original ARIADNE project produced some excellent guides. Consequently, some effort has been put into finding and reviewing external training resources as well, so that anyone using the Training Hub can find sufficient information to improve their knowledge at a basic level minimum on each of the topics.

The Transnational Access web pages will also be moved to the Training Hub for all subsequent calls (the next is due in September 2020 for visits during 2021). Figure 24 shows some of the training resources gathered for the topic “Managing datasets from large archaeological projects” and the type of information provided for each item.

To date, seven of the ten topics are complete enough to be launched with the upgraded website, and the remaining three will be completed during Period 2 (M19-M36) of the project. Yet to be completed are:

- “Defining and implementing a Data Management Plan (DMP)” – this will be done with the launch of the ARIADNEplus DMP template in the next period
- “Using Domain vocabularies to describe datasets” – to be done once this work has been completed (WP4)
- “Use of the ARIADNE+ Portal (data and services)” – this will be worked upon as new services and tools are added to the portal

⁴ D2.1 Initial Report on Community Needs, October 2019

Introduction

Archaeological projects can generate large quantities of data in varied formats and increasing dataset sizes as digital technologies are now used more frequently in conjunction with standard methods. In order to ensure the sustainability and "FAIRness" of this data, careful planning and management of these datasets is required. The University of York's Archaeology Data Service (ADS) Guides to Good Practice provide an excellent starting point and cover the most common data types for the complete project life cycle.

Title	Description	Source (URL)	Type	Level
Archaeology Data Service / Digital Antiquity – Guides to Good Practice	The Guides to Good Practice were originally produced by ADS and have been updated and expanded over the years in collaboration with various initiatives and Digital Antiquity in the US.	ADS (Guide Aims)	Web pages	Intermediate-Advanced
Digital Archiving	Introduction to the Guides with an overview of Digital Archiving	ADS	Web pages	Intermediate
The Project Lifecycle	Managing the processes of data creation and curation through the different project stages.	ADS	Web pages	Intermediate
Basic Components	How to create, curate and archive a cross selection of data formats including text, images, audio and video.	ADS	Web pages	Intermediate
	<i>Data Collection and Fieldwork: Guidelines for Aerial, UAV and Marine Survey, Geophysics, Laser Scanning, Close-Range Photogrammetry and Dendrochronology.</i>	Various authors	Web pages	Advanced
Aerial Survey for Archaeology	Covers the creation and preservation of digital resources resulting from aerial photography (incorporating optical and infra-red imagery collected from an airborne platform), satellite and airborne remote sensing (using a variety of sensors), and archaeological interpretations made from such data sources. As most of the raw data sources considered in this Guide are commercial products, or are not created and managed in digital format, detailed archiving advice is not appropriate for many primary data sources. Instead, archiving guidelines focus on secondary data such as archaeological interpretations and mapping.	ADS Bob Bewley, Danny Donoghue, Vince Gaffney, Martijn van Leusen, Alicia Wise and Kieron Niven	Web pages	Advanced

Figure 24. Information provided on “Managing datasets from large archaeological projects”

Finally, the Training Hub will also be used to promote both project-organised and relevant external training events, once these begin again. The creation of webinars is not anticipated to happen until a stable and complete new version of the Portal becomes available.

4.3 Short videos for communicating the scientific results

The new section of the web site “Activities and resources” is designed to include a series of short videos about various topics relevant for the project and for specific areas of interest, e.g. mapping between different schemas, data management plans, TNA, and so forth.

Through these short videos, scientific communication about the project’s outreach will be faster and more dynamic than traditional communication means, thus reaching a wider audience.

The Project Management Team has prepared a preliminary list of ideas for the topics and has identified project partners that will be responsible for the preparation of the related videos.

PRISMA’s team will ensure technical assistance in the production of the videos.

Preliminary list of topics

- *What is ARIADNEplus?* Presenter: Franco Niccolucci (PIN)
- *The ARIADNEplus workflow.* Presenter: Julian Richards (UoY-ADS)
- *The ARIADNEplus Cloud.* Presenter: Carlo Meghini (CNR)
- *How will ARIADNE impact on archaeologists’ work?* Presenter: Guntram Geser (SRFG)
- *Why do I need to write a DMP for my data?* Presenter: Paola Ronzino (PIN)
- *How can I become part of the ARIADNE network?* Presenter: Paola Ronzino (PIN)
- *Synergies with other projects – SEADDA.* Presenter: Holly Wright (UoY-ADS)
- *AO-CAT: essential data for the ARIADNEplus Catalogue.* Presenter: Achille Felicetti (PIN)
- *Mapping your data to AO-CAT.* Presenter: Achille Felicetti (PIN)
- *Mapping your data: VMT (Vocabularies Matching Tool) and Time Spans.* Presenter: Douglas Tudhope (USW)
- *Training and TNA in ARIADNEplus.* Presenter: Sheena Bassett (PIN)

The first two videos to be published on the website introduce the broad topic of what a research infrastructure is, with an introduction to the project, presented by the project coordinator and the data aggregation workflow established by the project for aggregating content provided by partners, introduced by the deputy coordinator. Both will contain links to more specific videos, anticipating the viewer the overall structure of the section.

The Board of Directors will supervise and review the content of the videos, thereby ensuring its scientific quality. Also, compliance with the European Union requirements for accessibility will be ensured, thus allowing inclusive access to the resources.

Each short video will last up to five minutes at most, to hold the attention of the viewer and focus on the important concepts. At the end of each video, references to resources related to the specific topic will be provided so the viewer can deepen their acquired knowledge.

To ensure consistency, the short videos will all have the same format, with a background showing the ARIADNEplus logo, and a cover and end credit page designed specifically for this purpose.

The Zoom platform has been chosen to produce the videos, as it allows users to run a presentation, and appear in a box in the top right-hand corner of the screen while the presentation is running. By following the simple tutorial prepared by the editorial committee/advisory board, each partner will be able to easily produce an efficient product, overcoming the difficulties we are all facing due to the pandemic.

The first video, also to be used as guidance for the others, is expected to be available by the end June or early July.

The series of videos will be published on the website using the Vimeo platform, as this is considered to be more suitable for professional purposes than YouTube.

Figure 25. A mock-up of a video.

4.4 Printed material & templates

Assuming that physical events will return, a poster will be produced to highlight the outputs from the project such as the new data, tools and services developed for the Portal, the Training Hub, etc.

4.5 Publications and internal reports

The Project Newsletter will continue to be published every three months with a view to increasing its circulation and reach via the Community pages.

Within the project (as part of the work in WP4, Task 4.4), several sub-domains have been identified who are currently working on their specific vocabularies and mappings (as part of the AO-CAT):

- Paleo-anthropology
- Bioarchaeology and Ancient DNA
- Environmental Archaeology
- Inorganic materials study
- Dating

- Field Survey
- Archaeological finds made by general public
- Remote Sensing
- Standing Structures
- Spatio-temporal data
- Maritime and underwater archaeology
- Archaeological fieldwork
- Inscriptions
- Burials

As part of this work in progress, the partners involved will produce short reports which are of interest to their colleagues and peers as well as the wider community. These internal reports will be produced and circulated to the ARIADNEplus Community to provide a comprehensive overview of the many different types of archaeology disciplines involved in the project and the challenges and solutions upon which each has decided. Some of these reports may also be the basis for subsequent journal articles and papers. One such example is the Data Aggregation Pipeline: User Guide – this document is the manual used by the partners to prepare and upload their datasets and is being updated as new types of datasets are added to the aggregation process. Not only it is a practical manual for mapping data, but it also contains a section “Background: why are we doing this?” which is a very readable explanation of the objectives and chosen solutions for the data aggregation, which would appeal to a wider audience.

4.6 Events

The main events for archaeologists during the next period (M19-M36) continue to be Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) and the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA). Three of these conferences will take place during Period 2:

- 26th EAA Annual Meeting - Virtual, 24 - 30 August 2020
- CAA 2021 in Limassol, Cyprus, 14-18 June 2021
- 27th EAA Annual Meeting - Kiel, Germany, 8 - 11 September 2021

In addition, partners will be encouraged to participate in events relating to many new fields of research (Bioarchaeology, aDNA, Environmental Studies etc.) and also those attended by computer scientists to disseminate the ARIADNE Infrastructure.

Finally, the WP7 team will encourage and support partners who wish to organise their own project-related regional/national events.

5 Conclusions

The primary lesson learned during the COVID-19 lockdown, which lasted from end of February until mid-May in Italy, but is ongoing in other parts of Europe, is that online communication can be as valid as meeting in person. ARIADNEplus promptly organised events with short notice to provide an alternative to planned meetings. But the result was beyond expectation: they were not just substitutes, but allowed the project to reach a much larger audience than a traditional conference or workshop (see the Events table, last lines). Even the online General Assembly proved to be better attended than those which are held in person.

The Italian workshop of April 3 was a reaction against the sad time that Italy and other EU countries were enduring during this time. The lockdown stopped normal life, and the death toll was increasing every day. It was organised in little more than a week with 20 presenters and some 250 followers on you tube. Conceived as a manifesto for *Research must go on* and to promote solidarity among scholars (#inthistgether was the workshop hashtag), it turned out to be one of the best surveys of the current state of the art in Italy.

Figure 26. A (partial) group photo of the speakers at the April 3 virtual workshop.

This workshop paved the way for the successful ARIADNEplus online General Assembly of 15 April, where not only all partners attended with more than one participant, but we also took stock of the project progress in a synthetic and productive way.

The two events enabled the organisation of a wider event, the European workshop co-organised on May 27th 2020 by ARIADNEplus and another project with the support of the European Commission, which put together experts from all Europe and had more than 2,500 views.

We will not abandon the organisation of meetings in person, as direct contact is invaluable and the success of many of the online events were due to reliance on already established collaborative relationships, but the past difficulties have shown us that a combination of online events and traditional in-person meetings is the key to success.

The only negative side is that planning is difficult, if not impossible. Organising a traditional conference for winter 2020/2021 is too risky and the pandemic may restart in new forms after the summer and create the same difficulties.

In conclusion, the key solution is flexibility: take all the opportunities to meet together but be ready to go online if necessary, and structure communication material to take the best of the two worlds, the virtual and the real, *quam minimum creduli postero*.

Figure 27. A photo of the April 15 ARIADNEplus Virtual General Assembly